

Coronal imaging of active eclipsing binaries: ER Vul and XY UMa

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Abstract

We present the coronal imaging of two active eclipsing binaries, ER Vul and XY UMa based on the X-ray data obtained from the XMM-Newton satellite. The results indicate that these systems are very soft X-ray sources, with a majority of the X-rays coming below 2 keV energy. The X-ray light curves show orbital modulation with an apparent primary eclipse, and modelling of the X-ray light curves reveals that both components of these systems are active, with the primary component being more X-ray bright than the secondary. Furthermore, results from the coronal imaging indicate that the coronae of both components are connected for the detached and semidetached binaries ER Vul and XY UMa, respectively. In the case of XY UMa, a highly active region near the coronal connection region is found, which is twice as bright as the second component in the system. Three flaring events are detected in the binary system XY UMa, which originated in the same active region that lies somewhere in between the two binary components.

1 Introduction

Magnetic fields generated inside cool stars by dynamos can give rise to a range of phenomena like sunspots, flares, and activity cycles. These phenomena can be observed across a range of wavelengths, from X-rays to radio waves (see reviews Favata & Micela, 2003; Güdel, 2004; Strassmeier, 2009). X-ray emissions from these stars typically come from thermal plasma in magnetic-coronal loops and can provide insight into the outermost parts of stellar atmospheres. As a star's rotation period decreases, magnetic activity increases and reaches to a saturation point around a Rossby number of 0.13. In the saturation region, the X-ray luminosity becomes about 1/1000th of the star's bolometric luminosity (Pizzolato *et al.*, 2003). There are various theories to explain this saturation, including saturation of the internal dynamo (Vilhu & Walter, 1987), maximum coverage of active regions on the star's surface (Vilhu, 1984), stripping of the corona due to increased rotation (Jardine & Unruh, 1999), and concentration of magnetic flux at the poles (Solanki *et al.*, 1997). The saturation phenomenon is seen in cool short-period binaries and young stars, while older single stars and long-period binaries follow the activity-Rossby number relationship. The Short-period binaries with both components being late-type show enhanced levels of magnetic activities due to tidal locking. Such binaries can show coronal connections and can be termed coronally connected binaries (CCBs). CCBs could lead to complex magnetic topologies and hence can give rise to higher flaring rates in such systems. Since stars are spatially unresolved by current observational limits, most of our knowledge about the structure of the outer atmospheres of stars comes from indirect techniques, i.e. using X-ray data for Doppler imaging (Brickhouse *et al.*, 2001), (ii) using light curve inversion techniques (Siarkowski, 1992; Siarkowski *et al.*, 1996; Drake *et al.*, 2014; Singh & Pandey, 2022), and (iii) extrapolating surface magnetic maps (Hussain *et al.*, 2007; Johnstone *et al.*, 2010; Cohen *et al.*, 2010, etc).

Each method has its own advantages and disadvantages. We present the coronal images of the short-period eclipsing binaries ER Vul and XY UMa, obtained using the X-ray light-curve inversion technique, to investigate the coronae of these systems. ER Vul is a short-period ($=0.698095$ d) RS CVn binary with a spectral class of G1-2V + G3V (Hall, 1976; Hill *et al.*, 1990; Özavcı *et al.*, 2019). Çakırlı *et al.* (2003) showed both the components in the system are active with the secondary component being more active. An eclipse-like feature is reported by Brown *et al.* (2002) and Brown *et al.* (2004) in their study of ER Vul using coordinated Chandra and VLA radio observations. XY UMa on other hand rotates slightly faster than ER Vul with a rotation period of 0.47899824 d and a spectral class of G2V + K5V with a binary separation of 3.1 R_{\odot} (Pribulla *et al.* (2001). Both components are reported as active from the optical to X-ray regime (Bedford & Geyer, 1986; Hilditch & Bell, 1994). The phase-locked variations are seen in quiescent states of XY UMa in X-ray light curves (Bedford *et al.*, 1990; Jeffries & Bedford, 1990). We organize the paper as follows: the observations and data reduction are described in Section 2. The coronal imaging process is outlined in Section 3. Our results are discussed in Section 4 and our conclusions are presented in Section 5.

2 Observations and Data Reduction

Both stars XY UMa and ER Vul were observed by the XMM-NEWTON observatory on 28 March 2005 and 22 April 2016, respectively. The exposure times of the observations were 59.2 and 60.6 ks for XY UMa and ER Vul, respectively. The XMM-NEWTON consists of three X-ray telescopes with five detectors (2 MOS (Turner *et al.*, 2001), 1 PN (Strüder *et al.*, 2001), and 2 RGS (den Herder *et al.*, 2001)) covering an energy range of 0.15–15 keV. Other than these X-ray detectors, XMM-Newton provides simultaneous observations in UV and optical bands with its optical monitor payload (OM Mason *et al.*, 2001). The raw data was reduced using Sci-

ence Analysis System (SAS) v18.0.0 software where we have adopted standard procedures to generate science products. The source light curves were generated by accounting for the X-ray counts within the circular region of radius 50" for ER Vul and 52" for XY UMa. Further, the background light curves were generated from source-free regions in the same CCD with a similar extracted area as that of the source. Afterwards, the background subtraction and detector response effects were corrected using task EPICLCCORR.

3 Analyses and Results

3.1 Light Curves

Figure 1 shows the X-ray light curves for XY UMa and ER Vul with a time bin size of 200 s in the energy band of 0.3-10.0 keV. The opposite to the time-axis shows the orbital phase which is calculated from the ephemeris given by Pribulla *et al.* (2001) for XY UMa and by Harmanec *et al.* (2004) for ER Vul. Further, we have marked the flaring episodes in the same Figure as blue-shaded regions where the hardness ratio (=Hard-Soft/Hard+Soft; Hard and Soft are count rates in 0.2-10.0 keV and 0.3-2.0 keV energy band respectively) increases and follows a standard flare-like time profile. The hardness ratio of both the stars is found to be around -0.9 which indicates the X-ray flux of these stars is dominated by hot plasma with temperatures less than 2 keV making them very soft X-ray sources.

3.2 Coronal Imaging: X-ray Light Curve Modelling

CCBs are unresolved in X-rays, so indirect methods are used to infer the coronal properties of X-ray-emitting plasma. For our current analysis, we have used the 3D deconvolution method of Siarkowski (1992) and Siarkowski *et al.* (1996) to reconstruct the 3D coronal structures of each binary system. A detailed method is mentioned in (Singh & Pandey, 2022) In brief, the corona around each component in binary is generated with cubical bins of variable emission density [$f_{em}(x, y, z)$]. A visibility matrix (M) is calculated for each phase which contains information on which bins are visible at any given time by taking the bin value to 1 if the bin is visible. Further, the volume bins which are always visible or are always occulted are shut off from the model process as these bins do not affect the orbital modulation in the observed light curve. By doing so, our model can take care of the inclination angle of binary, thus an extension to the Siarkowski (1992) model. Once the visibility matrix is calculated for each observed orbital phase, the binary is then evolved with the orbital phase and the resulting light curve is calculated by integrating the emission density from all the visible bins at a given phase. The discrepancy between the modelled light curve and the observed one is taken care of by the equation

$$f_{em}^{n+1}(x, y, z) = f_{em}^n(x, y, z) \frac{\sum_i \frac{F_o(\phi_i)}{F_c(\phi_i)} \mathbf{M}(\phi_i, x, y, z)}{\sum_i \mathbf{M}(\phi_i, x, y, z)}$$

where F_o and F_c represents observed and modelled flux value. The iteration process is stopped once the χ^2 between the observed and the modelled light curve become ~ 1 . A detailed view of the model and its assumptions are given in Singh & Pandey (2022). By using a cell size of $0.2 \times 0.2 \times 0.2 R_{\odot}^3$ an optimal solution of 3D coronal structure is obtained on the phase folded light curves of target stars. The results are

shown in Figure 2 and 3. From coronal images of both the target stars, the region connecting the binary components is brighter showing a coronal connection between the systems. For ER Vul, one side of the binary appears to be more bright than the other side as shown in Figure 2 (c) and (d) with active regions being distributed from low to mid-latitudes. The X-ray brightness of both components of the ER Vul system is found to be comparable, with the coronal connection region also exhibiting a similar degree of brightness. Because they are both of comparable size, this implies that both components have a similar level of coronal activity. The coronal images for XY UMa show the presence of three active regions on its primary component with two active regions facing away from the second component and one active region situated where coronae of both components are likely to connect (see Figure 3 (a) and (b). From Figure 3 (c) and (d), it appears as if the coronal connection is happening via the poles of each component with the primary and coronal connection region being about 4 and 2 times brighter than the secondary component.

4 Discussion

We have done an X-ray temporal study of two active CCBs, ER Vul and XY UMa. The X-ray light curves of both the CCBs, exhibit a highly dynamic nature with the presence of at least one flaring event. Analysis of the phase-folded light curves revealed that the variability is likely caused by orbital modulation. This is evident as the X-ray flux is found to be at its minimum near primary and secondary eclipses. However, it is possible that the variability seen during out-of-eclipse periods is caused by active regions that survive multiple orbital cycles. It is important to note that while the observed variability in the X-ray light curves is consistent with orbital or rotational modulation, there may also be a significant degree of random variability present that cannot be unambiguously attributed to these factors. The presence of orbital modulation in X-rays among eclipsing binaries is a relatively rare occurrence. However, a limited number of examples have been documented in the literature (e.g. Agrawal & Vaidya, 1988; Bedford *et al.*, 1990; Siarkowski, 1992; Siarkowski *et al.*, 1996; Drake *et al.*, 2014). The X-ray light curves of the binary system ER Vul shows similarity to the O'Connell-like effect, with the ratio of brightness at Maximum I to Maximum II being around 1.5. Previous studies on ER Vul's X-ray observations did not find any evidence of orbital modulation (White *et al.*, 1987; Brown *et al.*, 2002, 2004). However, further analysis of the X-ray light curves through modelling revealed that one side of each binary component has more active regions than the other. The active regions are responsible for the X-ray emission and the observed variability in the X-ray light curves. Additionally, the coronal images of ER Vul show a coronal connection located near the equator. The X-ray light curve of XY UMa displays three minima, with the primary eclipse at phase 0.0 being the deepest, a secondary eclipse at phase 0.5, and a dip near phase 0.75. The reason for the third minimum at phase 0.75 could be one or a combination of two factors: (i) an active region passing over the limb of the primary star, and (ii) the presence of an intra-binary plasma component that is being eclipsed. The X-ray light-curve modelling suggests that the second scenario is the most likely explanation for the observed third dip. Additionally, the intra-binary active region is found to be rela-

Figure 1: X-ray light curves of ER Vul and XY UMa as observed by XMM-Newton with time bin-size of 200 s. The phase values as shown opposite to the time axis are calculated using the ephemeris given in the text. The blue-shaded regions refer to flare duration and are marked by FN, where N = 1,2,3,4.

tively twice as bright as the secondary star. XY UMa has already been studied in X-rays by Jeffries (1998) and Gong *et al.* (2016), but no X-ray eclipses were found. However, using EXOSAT data, Bedford *et al.* (1990) discovered unambiguous evidence of the primary eclipse in X-rays. The coronal images suggest that the presence of intra-binary magnetic fields is independent of whether the binary is detached or semi-detached. However, certain similarities can be observed between the two systems, including the fact that they are both fast rotators with rotation periods shorter than one day, both contain a G2V type star as the primary component and a late-type star as the secondary component, and both are tidally locked. Based on the aforementioned similarities between the two systems, it is our hypothesis that coronal connections are likely to occur in short-period binary systems. If this hypothesis is proven to be valid, it would suggest that systems of the W UMa type have the highest potential for exhibiting coronal connections.

We have also observed flaring events in ER Vul and XY UMa. In the case of XY UMa, three flaring episodes have been observed with all being near the primary eclipse which may be attributed to the same active region. It appears that the recurrent flares in the same active region are caused by an interplay of complex magnetic topologies of the primary and secondary components in the system which is happening near the coronal connection. From the coronal images of XY UMa, the coronal connection region near the positive z-direction is brighter than the connection region near the negative z-direction. So it is more plausible that this upper coronal connection region is causing the flares.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, this study has carried out coronal imaging of two CCBs, ER Vul and XY UMa. The results indicate that these CCBs are very soft X-ray sources, with a majority of the X-rays coming below 2 keV energy, consistent with the observations of many short-period binaries in the past. The

X-ray light curves show orbital modulation with a clear primary eclipse, and modelling of the X-ray light curves reveals that both components of the CCBs are active, with the primary component being more X-ray bright than the secondary. Furthermore, results from the coronal imaging indicate that the coronae of both components are connected for the detached and semidetached binaries ER Vul and XY UMa. In the case of XY UMa, a highly active region near the coronal connection region was discovered, which is twice as bright as the secondary component in the system. The timings of flaring events along with the extracted coronal images of XY UMa indicate that the origin of all flares observed in this study originated from a common active region which is located somewhere in the coronal connection region. These findings provide valuable insights into the nature of CCBs and the mechanisms that drive their X-ray emission.

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Figure 2: Results of the X-ray light-curve modelling for the ER Vul. (a) Top view: a view of the upper hemisphere as seen by an observer at the top of the orbital plane, (b) bottom view: a view of the lower hemispheres as seen by an observer at the bottom of the orbital plane, (c) front view: 0° - 180° longitudinal view of the orbital plane from the front side (d) back view: 180° - 360° longitudinal view of the orbital plane from the backside, (e) the best-fit modelled light curve along with the observed light curve. The white dashed circles show the extent of the photosphere of primary and secondary.

Figure 3: Same as Figure 2 but for XY UMa.

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